

Morbusus excludens: The Pathogen of Suicide^a

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a- Reproduction of the last paragraphs of the book “What is suicide”.(1)

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Being able to connect with people from all over the world is vital. It seems that suicide only occurs in the presence of an exclusion event. Human beings are part of a social fabric that constitutes their existence. All of this makes us recognize

the importance of others in the context of suicide. The experience of feeling excluded is a common theme for suicidal individuals. A breakdown in social connections leads to a sense of existential despair. Factors such as lack of friends,

unemployment, financial instability, and social isolation can contribute to this feeling. Suicide often occurs in the context of segregation, which can act as a vehicle for spreading negative influences to vulnerable individuals. This exclusionary agent can be called ***Morbosus excludens*** and the vector of ***Excluder***. The feeling of exclusion can manifest as the end of a relationship, osteoarthritis leading to immobility, diabetes preventing the enjoyment of delicious chocolate cake, sexual abuse diminishing the pleasure of sex, or childhood violence resulting in developmental dysfunction, neurological aspects of the emotional system, unemployment, a packet of rice at R\$20.00 that excludes food, gasoline at R\$7.00 that prevents travel, and so on. The Excluder infects humans with exclusionary morbidity. In some more resilient people, with a more competent emotional immune system, it can be asymptomatic, cause mild depressive or anxious symptoms, or trigger suicidal illness in those who are less emotionally robust. The disease caused by ***Morbosus excludens*** contamination needs to be well diagnosed for appropriate interventions.

Morbosus excludens inoculation is often carried out in remote times, even in early childhood, altering the subject's neurobiological development and personality formation. Violence in the domestic environment and other social adversities tend to promote harm in interpersonal relationships and shift the search for pleasure naturally centered on

people to things. Events that promote harm to objectified fetishistic pleasure can trigger suicidal symptoms. This is the case with post-bariatric surgery patients who take great pleasure in eating and are prevented from eating large quantities of food and may have a strong tendency to commit suicide. Any change in sources of pleasure must be very well planned to avoid further damage.

In this reified universe in which we live, where the rule of the game is to be able to include yourself and exclude others, it is almost impossible not to be infected by ***Morbosus excludens***. However, the countless mechanisms of human adaptations can leave it in a latent state - such as the chickenpox virus, which, when experiencing great acute stress, triggers herpes zoster - and can break out into illness in a moment of suffering.

200 years ago, the cause of puerperal fever that killed many women was a mystery. Without knowledge of the pathogenic germs that cause gynecological infections, the existence of a miasma as an agent that promotes that disease was proposed.(2) We are not as far removed from the unknown as they are when we talk about the causes of suicide.

Today we can identify a virus causing damage to our computers and we lack an instrument to capture the etiological agent of suicide.

Under the microscope lens of phenomenology, we can visualize ***Morbosus excludens*** infecting the For-

itself and altering the presence of being-in-the-world. *Dasein* parasitized by morbid exclusion manifests different forms of difficulties with integration with the Whole, one of which is suicide. The robustness of For-itself will be related to the neurobiological conditions described. Each emotional and cognitive complex is related to the neuronal circuitry, predisposing to greater or lesser virulence of ***Morbosus exclusionens***.

If so, many questions emerge from this. In one of them, we could wonder if there would be any natural proposal for this frequent exclusionary behavior. Would aggressiveness ultimately mean that the strongest would prevail and eliminate the weakest?(3) Perhaps, the origins of this phenomenon are on the opposite side of this. The anthropology of exclusion may arise from the need for differentiation to better adapt to the external environment. Once differentiated, the being ends up no longer being the same as others.

Being different, it ends up excluded or excluding. Does a long process of natural

evolution and the constant need for the readaptation of beings end up generating the exclusionary agent? Is this how mutations generated COVID-19 and stress formed ***Morbosus excludens***? May answers come beyond epidemiology.

We can summarize our proposal for suicide prevention through the rapid identification of the excluding agent and its elimination. Just as *Aedes aegyptis* seeks to silently suck blood from the victim's heel, out of sight of the poor guy becoming bashful, it is not always so clear what the Excluder is, requiring individual work in the psychotherapeutic setting to determine it. But there is always an aggressor agent, who is the excluder, to balance the affectivity of the being. Human emotions, described as affections, come from the state of being affected by something. There will always be something external that affects it, in the way said by José Saramago in his Gospel according to Jesus Christ: "He cried because they made him cry, and he will cry because of that same and only reason".(4)

Referências:

1. Rodrigues JFR. O que é o suicídio: perfil epidemiológico de suicídio na cidade de Marília: proposições para prevenção. São Paulo: Dialética; 2022. 312 p.
2. Bryan CJ. Handwashing and Changing the Status Quo. Rethinking suicide: why prevention fails, and how we can do better. New York (NY): Oxford; 2022. p. 123-52.
3. Darwin C. A origem das espécies. São Paulo (SP): Martin Claret; 2014. 572 p.
4. Saramago J. O Evangelho segundo Jesus Cristo. São Paulo (SP): Companhia de Bolso; 2005.